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Legislation

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Euratom Research and Training Programme (2014-2018) – Council Regulation (Euratom) No 1314/2013 of 16 December 2013 on the Research and Training Programme of the European Atomic Energy Community (2014-2018) complementing the Horizon 2020 – The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p. 948).

H2020 Specific Programme – Council Decision 2013/743/EU of 3 December 2013 establishing the Specific Programme Implementing Horizon 2020 - The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p. 965).

Rules for Participation (RfP) – Regulation (EU) No 1290/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 of December 2013 laying down the rules for the participation and dissemination in Horizon 2020 – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p.81).

Financial Regulation (FR) – Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 966/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on the financial rules applicable to the general budget of the European Union (OJ L 298, 26.10.2012, p.1).

Rules of Application (RAP) – Commission Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 1268/2012 of 29 October 2012 on the rules of application of l Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 966/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the financial rules applicable to the general budget of the Union (OJ L 298, 26.10.2012, p.1).

Finding Endometriosis using Machine Learning: FEMaLe

1. ABOUT CORRELATE

Correlate provides a secure, easy, and flexible solution to synthesize data and information through a non-intrusive, lightweight, high performance, cost-efficient, easy-to-use desktop and mobile friendly web app that connects multi-cloud services. Correlate.com is a Software as a Service (SaaS) application enabling a transparent and augmented layer on top of other online digital activities, systems, and apps. The user correlates their digital asset with a link (URI) which is dragged and dropped into private or team-shared boards where information is further organized, annotated, and accessed by all collaborators.

The main features of Correlate are:

- Boards, in which information is stored and emails and files are accessible through
- Teams, in which boards are shared and collaborated on with other users
- Integrations, in which files stored in different cloud accounts and emails stored in different email accounts are made accessible.

Figure 1. Overview of Correlate platform

2. CORRELATES ROLE IN THE FEMaLe PROJECT

Correlate will be used as a platform to support the sharing and distribution of information throughout the FEMaLe project. Correlate is in the beta stage of development and will be developed during the FEMaLe project based on the needs of the project and the partners.

3. NEEDS ASSESSMENT OF CORRELATE IN FEMaLe PROJECT

Before the updated use of the Correlate platform in the FEMaLe project, planned for March 2022, two initiatives were conducted to assess the needs in the project and understand how Correlate can support the needs. First, a survey was conducted and sent out to the partners. The questions in the survey included the use of cloud services and other software tools and requested features in software tools used for the project. 19 FEMaLers answered the survey.

1. What is/are the main workpackage(s) you are involved in with the FEMaLe project?

2. Which of the following services do you use for document repository in your work?

3. Which of the following tools do you use for collaborating on documents with colleagues?

4. Do you have a Gmail account dedicated for work purposes?

5. Which software tools do you use for communicating with colleagues?

Secondly, a workshop was held in Aarhus on 3 November 2021 with eight participants. The workshop intended to get a broad understanding of the need for Correlate in the project and provide the possibility for the participants to test the platform and provide their feedback. The workshop included the four main parts:

1. *Focus group discussion*, with general questions about which features were needed in Correlate to support the project.
2. *Usability testing*, in which the participants tried out the platform and provided their feedback in each step.
3. *Focus group discussion*, with specific questions about the opinion of Correlate after having tried out the platform.
4. *User prototyping*, showing the participants prototypes of upcoming features in Correlate and letting the participants create their own rapid prototypes on paper.

In each step of the workshop the participants first went through a silent ideation process of writing their answers to the questions on post it notes and secondly sharing their opinion in a discussion with the rest of the group. Notes were taken during the discussions and the Post-it notes along with the prototypes were collected. Since a lot of features and ideas were generated during the workshop a section was also added to discuss the prioritisation and most important features to implement before the platform was used in the project.

After the workshop, the survey as well as the insights from the workshop were summarized into features that should be developed to support the project. Prioritization was done based on the discussions in the workshop as well as general estimations from the development team at Correlate. It was identified that the most important aspect to focus on was to increase usability through several quick fixes on the platform and to develop a product walkthrough to better onboard new users. Based on the feedback a roadmap was developed by Correlate and shared with the participants of the workshop.

4. ROADMAP

The following table (Table 1.) shows the planned features and improvements of the Correlate platform based on the feedback collected in the survey and the workshop. The roadmap should be seen as a general plan to guide the development of the platform and can change based on new feedback and insights from the users as well as from the development team at Correlate.

Table 1. Roadmap for development of features in Correlate

Feature	Description	Status
Add members to teams	Clarify button for adding members to a team and clarify UX copy	Completed
View team members	Let all users in a team see the team members and their user permission	Completed
Drag and drop several items	Let users mark several items (notes, files etc.) in a board and drag and drop them	Completed
Alphabetic sorting of boards	Let users sort boards in a team alphabetically	Completed
Bug fixes	Fix bugs that are noticed by users such as getting scrolled up in boards	Will be fixed continuously as new bugs are identified
SharePoint Integration	Research possibility of sharing documents from SharePoint in a user-friendly way	Planned to be completed by March
Opening files	Change the logic behind how users open files in Correlate	Planned to be completed by March
Adjust notifications	Decrease number of notifications so that users only receive a limited number	Planned to be completed by March
Adjust user permissions	Allow several users to have the highest level of permission and manage the team	Planned to be completed by March
Version history of boards	Be able to switch between different versions of the board and track changes over time	Planned to be completed by March
Templates	Provide templates to get started more easily with creating new	Planned to be completed by March
Product walkthrough	Provide a product walkthrough with new users getting started with Correlate	Planned to be completed by March
Task list	Create and assign tasks to other users	Planned to be completed after March
First version homescreen	Home screen including repository, favorite boards and teams, and personal boards	Planned to be completed after March

Communicate	Direct messaging feature	Planned to be completed after March - research in progress
Organizational level	Be able to have an organizational level for the entire project with shared information across teams	Planned to be completed after March
Home screen version 2	Including timeline and calendar for the project, KPIs for the project, etc.	Planned to be completed after March
File management	Being able to lock files and have an individual repository per team	Planned to be completed after March
Public sharing of boards version 2	Be able to share boards as embedded links on other sites and make teams public	Planned to be completed after March
Project layer	Add an extra layer between teams and boards	Planned to be completed after March
Profiles	Be able to create personal profiles on Correlate and search for people/expertise on organizational and team level	Planned to be completed after March

